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POST-FIRE FOREST RESTORATION FOR THE TROPICS

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Abstract

Forests play an important role in improving the natural ecological environment, have great effects in responding to and minimizing damage caused by climate change and natural disasters such as floods, landslides, greenhouse gas effects. The impact from forest fires is huge, it directly impacts climate change. Even under normal conditions, the fires have destroyed the vegetation and animals living in the forest, including precious trees and animals that need to be preserved, making their numbers less and less. Putting many organisms on the endangered list, causing biodiversity loss and ecological imbalance. In order to regenerate those forests, in addition to effort and money, it also takes time corresponding to the age of the forest to regenerate and develop the forest as before. Therefore, active efforts are needed to prevent forest fires and effectively restore the affected forests after fires.

Keywords: Forest fire, climate change, forest restoration, tropics.

Introduction

Since the 1980s, severe wildfires have been on the rise globally. In 2015, the occurrence of fires in the Brazilian Amazon increased by 36% compared to 12 years ago [1]. In the same year, the rate of daily emissions from peat fires in Indonesia exceeded the rate of fossil fuel emissions in the United States, causing serious environmental damage and human health problems throughout the Southeast [2]. The 2019-2022 bushfires that occurred in Australia, burning more than 10 million hectares of forest, have shown that the nature of global wildfires is changing, with increasing scale, nature and intensity. Wildfires are responsible for 5–10% of global greenhouse gas emissions [3], of which 84% of total global fire emissions originate in the tropics [4]. Besides their impact on the global carbon cycle, rain-forest fires are detrimental to forest ecosystems and local communities. They not only reduce biomass but also affect species composition, change water and nutrient cycles, increase the risk of flooding and erosion, and threaten local livelihoods by burning farmland, business and home. Additionally, these fires have a devastating impact on local wildlife as animals cannot escape the fires or are threatened by loss of habitat, food, and shelter.

Vietnam is located in the tropics, but the climate of Vietnam is distributed into 3 regions according to the Köppen climate classification with the North having a humid tropical climate. The North consists of 2 seasons: Summer and Winter. The North Central, Central and South Central regions have a tropical monsoon climate, the southernmost regions of Central Vietnam and the South have tropical savanna characteristics. At the same time, because it is located on the Southeast edge

of the Asian mainland, bordering the East Sea (part of the Pacific Ocean), it is directly affected by the trade monsoon climate, which often blows in the regions of the world. low latitude. The South usually has 2 seasons: the rainy season and the dry season. The data of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam show that, in the 10 years of 2009-2018, forest fires have destroyed nearly 22,000 hectares of Vietnam's forests, causing great economic losses to the country. The peak of this period was in 2010, about 6,723 hectares of forest were destroyed by big fire. In 2007, there were 749 forest fires causing damage of 4,188 ha. In recent years, although the area of forest burned has decreased sharply, there are still unexpected and complicated developments that are unpredictable. In 2017, a sharp increase in rainfall made the weather less dry and hot, contributing to reducing the area of forest burned to the lowest level in the past decade, the damage level was only 471.7 hectares, a decrease of about 80 percent. % compared to 2016 (3,320 ha). By 2018, the damage caused by forest fires had increased compared to 2017 (739.1 ha), but in general, the damage was still low compared to other years. However, in the 10 months of 2019, the burned forest area increased to 2.7 thousand hectares, 3.6 times higher than 2018. Especially, in the peak months of the dry and hot season, many areas Vietnam's forests are in the state of warning of the risk of forest fires at level V (extremely dangerous level), the risk of forest fires is very high, causing the Government and ministries and branches to frequently issue urgent notices to forest fire prevention. Faced with this situation, it is necessary to effectively restore post-fire affected forests using a combination of several post-fire rehabil-

itation strategies in the humid tropics. A variety of restoration strategies can be applied in the restoration of moist tropical forests such as: natural regeneration, supporting natural regeneration (e.g. fire prevention, weed control, erosion control, etc.) replace ground soil, regenerate peat land), plant trees to cause forests...

Some measures to restore forests after fire

Ecosystem restoration includes many different strategies. The selection of an appropriate strategy should be based on a number of factors, including the local restoration context (e.g. topographic characteristics, frequency and severity of disturbances), constraints and limitations. resource constraints (e.g. available knowledge, technical capacity and funding.. Restoration goals can range from restoring pre-existing forest structure, functions and species composition, to restoration. restore desirable ecosystem services, such as maximizing carbon sequestration or enhancing biodiversity, creating forest landscapes for socioeconomic purposes[7].

Control the risk of forest fire

Although the fact that wildfire regimes are changing globally is widely acknowledged, the impact of such changes on restoration practices has so far not received much attention. In particular, knowledge of the characteristics of forest fires prior to recovery efforts is limited. This is remarkable, as the recovery potential of burned forests is largely determined by these characteristics. Ecosystem responses, including vegetation regeneration, fauna, hydrological processes and soil erosion, are affected by fire severity, described as loss. organic matter above and below ground. The severity of the fire can be explained by the physical properties of the fire, such as fire intensity, fire depth, and soil heating time. These fire characteristics - and their effects - are not common, and therefore need to be analyzed in their particular context. Despite the fact that humid rainforests are less prone to fires than dry forests, they

are more vulnerable to the effects of fire and recover more slowly than forests with longer fire histories. While severe fires in temperate and montane forests are mostly surface fires or intense, fast-spreading flames, most fires in the humid tropics do not spread rapidly and are not intense due to high fuel moisture content. In general, the resilience of burned forests decreases as the severity of the fire increases. However, in order to better understand and predict ecosystem responses to fire and develop effective recovery methods, specific interactions between measures of fire severity, soil and biological populations need to be studied further. This is especially true for the humid tropics, where the starting point for fire recovery is different and less well known than for fire-adapted systems.

Weed control

Eliminating invasive weeds and weeds can help increase the variety of natural regeneration by limiting competition for crops. A commonly used technique involves marking all naturally regenerated woody species or planted seedlings, and mowing the surrounding grass, but pruning is a laborious undertaking and is only suitable for small scale restoration projects. In addition, pruning tends to encourage grass to re-grow faster and therefore needs to be repeated often. An alternative to mowing is to press the grass with wooden planks. The pressed vegetation blocks sunlight, thereby killing the underlying weed layers and preventing further weed germination. Weed pressing also functions as an erosion control measure and helps reduce fire intensity. In addition, pressing weeds can have beneficial effects on seedling survival, such as by reducing soil temperature and light intensity. Although pressing is a laborious job, it requires less repetition than cutting. Another inexpensive method for competitive vegetation control is chemical weeding, or the use of herbicides. Especially in areas with high labor costs, chemical weeding is often applied instead of manual mowing.

Figure 1. Application of the herbicide Glyphosate (*N*- (phosphonomethyl) glycine)

Anti-erosion

Burned forest areas, especially on steep slopes, are susceptible to soil erosion due to reduced ground cover and canopy and altered soil physical properties[5]. To minimize this impact, erosion control measures can be implemented. One such practice is mulching, i.e. covering the surface with a layer of organic material to conserve soil and water and create favorable conditions for

plant growth. A variety of materials can be used for this purpose, the most common of which are straw, forestry by-products and glass, a slurry of wood, paper fibers and water-insoluble binders. The effect of the coating is immediate and as some coating materials have been shown to be effective erosion treatments.

Figure 2. Some measures to prevent forest soil erosion after fire

Replace topsoil

Topsoil replacement, i.e. the transfer of soil containing leaf litter, soil microorganisms, plant debris and

seeds from a newly cleared area to a degraded area, is intended to accelerate the regeneration process. nature and restore plant communities.

Figure 3. Replacing topsoil with straw mulch

Although there is no literature on the use of topsoil to restore burned rainforests, the treatment has the potential to improve seedling conditions, especially where there is a layer of soil containing seeds and nutrients. organic matter on topsoil was consumed by a severe fire. Topsoil replacement has been found to facilitate the propagation of trees, vines, shrubs and herbs in degraded tropical dry forests.

Planting seedlings

Figure 4. Sowing seeds in the process of forest restoration

While direct seeding is considered an effective way to enrich existing vegetation, it is less suitable for restoring landscapes that have been severely degraded. In burned areas where seed mortality is generally high due to poor soil conditions, water aridity, species with thick seed coats (e.g. legumes) can help drought recovery. In peat bog forests, careful selection of species that can withstand both flooding and drought is needed to enhance seed and seedling survival.

Conclusion

Rainforest fires are increasing in size and their impacts extend beyond national boundaries. Therefore, improving the efficiency of forest restoration after fire becomes more important than ever. To be able to restore forests to the scale needed, it is important to create and maintain collaborative capacity and to focus on setting priorities for efficient resource allocation. Depending on the context of ecological and socio-economic restoration, specific measures are required for the most effective post-fire forest restoration. Simultaneously conduct long-term studies on forest recovery rates and identify different interventions appropriate to the fire characteristics and ecological conditions of each region.

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